

Recommended citation: Boelt, A. M., Bertel, L. B., Kolmos, A., & Clausen, N. R. (2019). A comparative curriculum analysis of two PBL engineering programs. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1415-1423). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656735.

A COMPARATIVE CURRICULUM ANALYSIS OF TWO PBL ENGINEERING PROGRAMS

A. M. Boelt¹

Ph.D. fellow

Aalborg Centre for Problem Based Learning in Engineering Science and Sustainability under the auspices of UNESCO, Aalborg University

Aalborg, Denmark

Email: boelt@plan.aau.dk

L. B. Bertel

Postdoc

Aalborg Centre for Problem Based Learning in Engineering Science and Sustainability under the auspices of UNESCO, Aalborg University

Aalborg, Denmark

Email: lykke@plan.aau.dk

A. Kolmos

Professor

Aalborg Centre for Problem Based Learning in Engineering Science and Sustainability under the auspices of UNESCO, Aalborg University

Aalborg, Denmark

Email: kolmos@plan.aau.dk

N.R. Clausen

Ph.D. fellow

Aalborg Centre for Problem Based Learning in Engineering Science and Sustainability under the auspices of UNESCO, Aalborg University

Aalborg, Denmark

Email: nclausen@plan.aau.dk

ABSTRACT

This paper presents preliminary findings from an ongoing cross-faculty research project on the future of problem-based learning at Aalborg University. The research project consists of a baseline study and a number of sub-projects, this particular case being part of the former, where a curriculum analysis is conducted to infer how PBL competencies are framed in formal curricula on 13 different educations. This paper includes two of these curricula in more detail.

PBL is hailed as an innovative approach to learning with a focus on authentic problems and student-directed learning. The formal structure has, from its conception been regarded as highly adaptable, enabling institutional and societal ambitions to be aligned. Students working

¹ Corresponding author

with a PBL curriculum are expected to develop a variety of competencies, both specific disciplinary and vocational, but also competencies directly related to the actual pedagogical approach. These competencies are internally dubbed 'PBL competencies', and as part of a new institutional strategy, these are to be included in formal curricula explicitly stating the progressive development throughout the educational cycle. This paper provides a comparative analysis of current institutional framing of PBL competencies in two formal curricula from two bachelor programmes of engineering education at AAU (Nanotechnology, and Biomedical Engineering and Informatics). Conducting a theoretically directed content analysis, each curriculum is analyzed for categories and themes related to the aforementioned PBL competencies. The research results will give insights into how the progression of these PBL competencies are described in the formal curricula. Preliminary results point to a diverse inclusion of PBL competencies within the selected formal curricula with little evidence of explicit formulations regarding the progression of these competencies, especially on later semesters.

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents initial findings, a methodological approach and a theoretical framework for conducting a directed content analysis of problem-based learning (PBL) curricula exemplified in two cases of engineering bachelor programs, Nanotechnology and Biomedical Engineering and Informatics. The research is part of an ongoing multi-faculty research project PBL Future at Aalborg University called PBL Future, encompassing a baseline study, of which the curriculum analysis is a part of, and a number of sub-projects. This analysis is part of the baseline study and research how PBL learning outcomes are described in selected formal curricula on bachelor and master programs.

Formal curricula is an interesting point of departure when researching educational programs and can be understood as cultural artefacts socially constructed by numerous actors with different agendas [1-2]. These networks of action are situated in specific systems of reality from which the document get meaning. Traversing the boundaries of national educational spheres, international processes such as the Bologna Process has influenced the development and structure of the formal curricula to meet a set of standardized descriptors categorized as knowledge, skills, and competences enabling comparisons of educational programs across Europe [3]. One argument for this transition to learning goals is to reform and modernize 'Europe's antiquated education system' by moving from teacher-centered teaching to student-centered learning, and recognizing 'the use of learning outcomes as the only logical approach' [4]. However, at Aalborg University a student-centered pedagogical approach to learning has been practiced since 1974, so in what ways are the university in need of modernization? The principles of the approach remain alive and well, but there is an institutional desire to review the principles to keep them relevant in the future to meet requests of industry 4.0 or develop the much-anticipated competences of the 21st century.

Interestingly, Voogt and Roblin [5] notes in their comparative analysis of frameworks describing 21st century competences, that two of the frameworks highlight PBL as a pedagogical technique supporting the acquisition of these competences, but some students still struggle to conceptualize and vocalize generic competences developed in a PBL environment.

Our and colleges' experience as project supervisors shows that students use the learning outcomes stated in formal curriculum as a checklist for potential assessment when they are

about to finalize projects. An unfortunate result might be learning directed to the test, which although participant-directed can put unconscious limitations on the work students pursue. From a strategic point of view however, descriptions of more generic learning outcomes in the formal curricula may prove a viable path to initiate students into the mystery of non-disciplinary competences. Researching formal curricula provides insights into how these are framed and described from an institutional perspective, and while the analysis naturally cannot illuminate us as to how the curricula are enacted, it can show us how and if the competences are present at all, and if so, how the development progresses over semesters.

In the following, we will briefly present the core tenets of the Aalborg Problem-based Learning model, the theoretical framework used to conduct the content analysis of the collected data, and the analytical constructs used to direct the analysis. Finally, we will present the initial findings of the research and discuss how these learning outcomes can be included in the formal curricula.

1 THE AAU MODEL OF PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING

Inspired by youth revolts and critical pedagogy in Europe, problem-based learning has been a central component of studying at Aalborg University since its inception in the 70's. Centered around authentic problems, students engage in problem-based and project-organized learning activities with high levels of autonomy and student-directed learning facilitated by supervisors and teachers [6-8]. The AAU model of problem-based learning is characterized by three core and interwoven clusters of learning principles [6]:

- **The learning approach:** An approach involving identification, analysis and solutions of authentic, practical or theoretical problems defined by students. Problems can vary in structure and complexity influencing the organization of learning activities, ranging from predefined cases to complex situated problems.
- **The social approach** to learning supports the learning approach, where learning is considered a collaborative social activity unfolding in interaction with peers, sharing and constructing knowledge together. Learning becomes an act of negotiation, the group setting the direction for their problem-solving.
- **The contents approach** is the last core principle, and covers selection of knowledge and skills. Working in a PBL environment is inherently interdisciplinary with learning spanning across multiple subject domains requiring the students to use a variety of sources and methods from different disciplines. Further, the learning is framed as a research process relating theory and practice enhancing students' understanding of the two when analysing and solving a particular problem.

According to Guerra [9] the presented learning principles, PBL fosters an environment in which students develop competences such as problem-solving skills, decision-making, self-directed learning, critical thinking, communication and teamwork. During the course of a project, students need to be mindful of project management, groupwork and collaboration, consequently developing learning strategies and gaining a diverse set of process competences while being socialized into a professional field and identity [7].

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In this section we will present the theoretical framework directing the analysis and discuss epistemological considerations of conducting a content analysis of the formal curricula, also known as the intended curricula.

2.1 Curriculum Making

Curriculum making exists on multiple levels; institutional, programmatic and classroom. The institutional level consists of a nexus of culture and society, whereas the curriculum on a programmatic level consist of syllabus and subject construction, descriptions and structures of school, programs and approaches to teaching, and last but not least stating criteria for successful graduation. The final level is the enacted or mediated curriculum unfolding in a classroom [10-11]. This analysis is thus limited in scope because of its singular focus on the programmatic level. However, it contributes valuable insights into and important understandings of the construction and framing of the structures within which the curriculum is enacted and experienced.

2.2 A Directed Content Analysis

The content analysis is informed by Krippendorff's methodological approach [12], and can be characterized as a directed content analysis with code schemas established by theory or concepts before the first reading. Krippendorff argues that a content analysis must be transparent in its approach, suggesting to applicate five basic elements providing a transparent framework:

1. **Body of text:** Formal curricula
2. **Research question or hypothesis:** How are PBL competences presented in the formal curricula
3. **Context in which the text has significance:** An integrated problem-based and project-organized curriculum
4. **Analytical constructs to process text:** Descriptions of PBL competences
5. **Inferences intended to answer a research question**

Since meaning is brought to texts by an interpreter, there is no single meaning to derive from text and the same text can be subjected to multiple and different analyses depending on context. Thus, there is a link between the text and outside phenomena, i.e. meaning exist as something outside the actual text and according to Krippendorff the 'analysist must look outside the physicality of the texts' to fully grasp its meaning [14].

2.3 Cases and Body of Text

The cases in this analysis are two educational programs; BSc in Engineering (Biomedical Engineering and Informatics) and BSc in Engineering (Nanotechnology with specialization on Physics) or (Nanotechnology with specialization in Biotechnology), hereafter BIO and NANO.² Both are three-year programs with a workload of 180 ECTS. As expected the courses and subjects depend on profession, but both programs have a course introducing students to problem-based learning on the first semester, presenting methodology and underlying premises of the approach, but also topics related to project management, collective learning approaches and more. The result of this becomes evident when presenting the initial findings.

² These are official titles from formal curricula.

The data used in the analysis are two formal curricula. Both are organized according to the Dublin Descriptors describing expected learning outcomes in categories of either knowledge, skills or competences [3]. The selected curricula each refer to a number of official governmental papers and internal regulations, the anticipated overall competences profile of the finished bachelor students, overall description of courses, pedagogical framings and assessment among other things. Since curricula are as different as the social actors and institutional bodies who produce them, a decision has been made to limit the scope to course descriptions. The formal curricula were read, selecting matching criteria of the mentioned PBL competences and coded in NVivo. The units of analysis are learning outcomes defined either as knowledge, skills or competences.

Though PBL is contextual and exemplary in practice, formulated learning outcomes relating what could be considered as prior developed PBL competences to a specific professional domain has been excluded in the analysis. This is due to the fact that students have difficulties transferring knowledge between fields [13], and any inclusion of domain specific competences in the guise of PBL competences would in this context require students to have transferable competences unbeknownst to the analyst.

2.4 Progressive PBL learning goals

Based on the learning principles/approaches presented earlier, a research group at Aalborg University has deduced four distinct competences developed by students' doing PBL. The PBL competences can be divided into four categories:

- **Problem-oriented competences** gained by engaging in authentic and complex problems through exemplary practice, activating prior knowledge to construct new knowledge in a context that requires this skill [14].
- **Interpersonal competences** developed by collaborating and negotiating with peers during participant directed projects.
- **Structural competences** related to project management or to paraphrase Anderson in Jonassen [15]; competences to externalize the sequence of cognitive operations.
- **Metacognitive competences** reaching across all of the above, characterized by the relation between the individual student and their learning processes.

These competences can only be developed in a reflective practice connecting theory and practice. Disbanding this dialectic results in mere trial-error processes and is not considered reflective practitioners engaging in double looped learning cycles. The dialectic relation means that students' learning experiences are directly related to their PBL practice and the collective and individual reflection of these experiences [14]. It also means that knowledge and skills stated as learning goals are complimentary to the development of PBL competences, and hence included in the content analysis.

Progressive PBL learning goals are then related to the development of generic PBL competences over the course of the whole education, and making this progressive development explicit to students in terms of expected learning outcomes.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial result of the analysis paints a similar picture of the two curricula: The majority of learning outcomes related to the development generic PBL competences are placed on the first semester with little evidence of progression in the course of the educational programs. In

the following we will elaborate more on the results by looking at each year including examples of learning outcomes.

It important to note that learning outcomes are not quantified meaning that one goal can contain a number of sub-goals. The weighting of the coding is done in such a manner that the selected weight of each text string is relative to the rest of the text corpus from which it originates. An interesting side note, and a sting maybe is that many formulations are lifted almost word to word from the national qualification framework without any further relation to the actual context or course, problematizing our own unending quest and obligations to prevent plagiarism.

Fig. 1. Treemap of NANO

Fig. 2. Treemap of BIO

The treemaps shown in figure 1 and 2 show that the majority of learning outcomes related to the development of generic PBL competences are placed on the first semester. The intended learning outcomes are described using the Dublin Descriptors [3], but more often than not only two of categories. It should be noted that the colors displayed in the treemaps are byproducts of the coding in NVivo, and has no interpretative value.

BIO and NANO share a similar structure during the first year, where students are introduced to PBL in 5 ECTS course, and in three projects dubbed P0, P1, P2. For each of these projects the students must hand in a process analysis describing their group work, project management and more. Already at the 2. Semester the presence of learning goals related to generic PBL competences are more limited, and for both BIO and NANO there are no learning goals related to development of interpersonal competences.

On the second year, the third and fourth semester, BIO has learning goals related to the aforementioned PBL competences. The learning goal addresses development of structural competences during project work. It was surprising to find that none of the other PBL competences were present as generic PBL learning goals.

The formal curricula shows that students fairly early are establishing a membership in their specialized education [16], where PBL is described in relation to professional and contextual problems not readily transferable as generic competences across knowledge domains without aid from supervisors [13]. The supervisors are tasked with bridging the paths for transfer, but by emphasizing learning outcomes as the 'only logic step' for modernizing educational programs and institutions there is a chance that students may only seek learning experiences that only 'hugs' [17] a set target rather than opening up or encouraging abstractive thinking

and development of metacognitive skills. A challenge when using explicitly stated learning outcomes in a PBL environment is ensuring student and teacher autonomy during the learning experience, but one could argue that using too explicit outcomes can affect the learning trajectory of students, rather than enabling themselves to navigate their path into both a university environment and a professional context.

4 CONCLUSION

Reading the formal curricula gives insights into the institutional framing of PBL competences, or intended curricula, but they do not tell us anything about the actual enactment of the curricula. The documents can serve as a basis for discussing institutional strategies and how the desired strategic ambitions of educational institutions can be implemented while maintaining a high degree of teacher autonomy, minimizing an instrumental approach. The bulk of generic PBL learning goals placed on the first and partly second semester stresses the important role that the supervisors play when it comes to helping students transfer competences across professional domains. According to Bernstein this can be difficult as the students on specialized educational programs develop subject loyalty in a self-perpetuating oscillating motion including teachers and lecturers. Of course, loyalty is by no means negative, but in this age of interdependency, loyalty needs to extend the borders of professional domains.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Prior, *Using Documents in Social Research*, Electronic. London : Sage Publications, 2003.
- [2] L. Prior, "Repositioning documents in social research," *Sociology*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 821–836, 2008.
- [3] Bologna Working Group on Qualifications Frameworks, *A Framework for Qualifications of the European Higher Education Area*. Copenhagen: Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, 2005.
- [4] S. Adam, "Learning Outcomes Current Developments in Europe: Update on the Issues and Applications of Learning Outcomes Associated with the Bologna Process," 2008.
- [5] J. Voogt and N. P. Roblin, "A comparative analysis of international frameworks for 21st century competences: Implications for national curriculum policies," *J. Curric. Stud.*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 299–321, 2012.
- [6] A. Kolmos and E. D. Graaff, "Problem-based and project-based learning in engineering education," in *Cambridge Handbook of Engineering Education Research*, A. Johri and B. M. Olds, Eds. Cambridge University Press, 2014, pp. 141–161.
- [7] X. Du and A. Kolmos, "Process competencies in a problem and project based learning environment," *Proc. 34th SEFI Annu. Conf.*, 2006.
- [8] F. Kjersdam and S. Enemark, *The Aalborg Experiment - Project Innovation in University Education*. Aalborg: Aalborg : Aalborg University Press, 1994.
- [9] A. Guerra, "Integration of Sustainability in Engineering Education: Why Is PBL an Answer?," *Int. J. Sustain. High. Educ.*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 436–454, 2017.
- [10] Z. Deng and A. Luke, "Subject Matter: Defining and Theorizing School Subjects," in *The SAGE Handbook of Curriculum and Instruction*, no. September 2016, F. M. Connelly, M. F. He, and J. Phillion, Eds. 2008, pp. 66–90.
- [11] I. Westbury, "Talk, decisions, and action in curriculum-making: reflections on the ILS and L97 case studies," *J. Curric. Stud.*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 803–814, 2016.
- [12] K. Krippendorff, *Content analyses : an introduction to its methodology*, 2nd ed. SAGE Publications, Inc, 2004.
- [13] A. Kolmos, X. Du, J. Holgaard, and L. P. Jensen, *Facilitation in a PBL environment*. 2008.
- [14] C. E. Hmelo-Silver, "Problem-Based Learning : What and How Do Students Learn ?," *Educ. Psychol.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 235–266, 2004.
- [15] David H. Jonassen, "Toward a design theory of problem solving," *Educ. Technol. Res. Dev.*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 63–85, 2000.
- [16] B. Bernstein, "On the curriculum," in *Class, Codes and Control: Towards a Theory of Educational Transmissions (Volume 3)*, Routledge, 2003.
- [17] D. N. Perkins and G. Salomon, "Transfer of Learning," *Int. Encycl. Educ. Second Ed.*, 1992.
- [18] S. T. Hopmann, "No child, no school, no state left behind: schooling in the age of accountability," *J. Curric. Stud.*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 417–456, 2008.